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Business Model Development and Adaption of VET Service Providers in International Contexts

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Abstract

Context: The attraction to internationalize vocational education and training (VET) generates various business models among German VET providers seeking new markets and expanding their portfolio of services internationally. To support German VET providers in their internationalization, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) has created two funding programs (BEX and IBB) for the development of international business models in VET. In the context of this paper, adaptations of the business models with regard to the course of the projects over both funding periods are considered in order to find out what factors were considered by the VET providers in that process.

Approach: 18 projects from two funding lines (BEX and IBB) were analysed, each project is a consortium of at least a VET provider and a research institution. The sample includes all funded projects in which at least one organization was funded subsequently in both funding lines. This allows for better comparability between the cases and between the two funding lines. The research design was thus constructed as a longitudinal study. The data includes project documents and qualitative interviews with project actors. The nine categories of the Business Model Canvas according to Osterwalder and Pigneur were applied to identify adoptions made in the business models of the selected projects.

Findings: Substantial changes to the original project planning with regard to the business models can be seen with reference to the reduction of the complexity of the offered VET services. Adjustments to the business models are primarily determined by industrial factors, especially with regard to the stakeholders involved, and changes based on market factors to adapt the VET services to the needs of partners and customers in the target country. A considerable part of the adjustments to the business models are also based on pandemic-related factors.

Conclusion: It can be assumed that the analyzed VET providers have a high level of problem-solving expertise due to the consortium approach. The digitalization of some elements of the business models can possibly be understood as an innovation driver so that innovations can be expected. Further research in the form of a journal contribution will look at these and other aspects in more detail. It would be necessary to consider degrees and patterns of innovation regarding the analysed projects and the database presented.

Keywords: vocational education providers, innovation, internationalisation, business model

1 Introduction and Problem Statement

The *international attractiveness* of dual vocational education and training (VET) creates new opportunities for education service providers from the German VET sector. It opens international markets to those VET providers who want to develop their business units. New markets require new offers and thus new processes to meet the customers' needs. This brings the question of the scope of business model-related innovations into focus.

As a *support for the sector* to internationalize its activities, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) created two successive funding programs, a first one supported the development of viable international business models ("Vocational Training Export BEX", 2010-2017). A second one provided financial support to providers for the demand-driven development and model implementation of education and training provision for international markets ("Internationalization of Vocational Education IBB", ongoing since 2017) (BMBF, 2017). Details have been presented in further research with regard to the predecessor funding program (BEX) and the successor funding program (IBB) (see e.g. Kühn, 2021; Kühn & Greppmair, 2021; Meyne, 2021; Peters & Krichewsky-Wegener, 2021; Siemer & Gessler, 2021).

These two funding lines represent the *context of the research*. Previous research in this context showed that most companies applying for support in IBB were just beginning to develop international activities at the time. Only half of the VET service providers in that funding line had an internationalisation strategy at the project start, while the other half had one under development or none (Kühn et al., 2020). From BEX to the beginning of IBB, Kühn & Greppmair (2021) identified, based on related samples, a number of lessons learned in different areas concerning the development of international business models (Kühn & Greppmair, 2021). VET service providers undertake certain adaptations of their business models related to the new challenges. Gessler et al. (2018) found that the developed business models are "not part of the standard offers of the company" (Gessler et al., 2019, p. 261). That means that the small and medium-sized enterprises need to handle uncertain novelties. Therefore, they are assumed to apply certain strategies. Coming back to the introductory research context, the VET service providers are required to develop (economically) sustainable business models, while the frame for this development in IBB appears broader to a certain degree in comparison to BEX. It is not yet clear, what (innovation) strategies lead the relevant processes of business model development and transfer. This research aims to identify adoptions done within the VET providers' business models within each funding program and between both programs. The sample consists of enterprises that were active in both contexts. The leading research questions for this research are: (1) *What adaptations have been made in the course of the projects with regard to the originally planned business models and why?* (2) *What can we learn about the strategic orientation of the adaptations identified?* This paper can be classified as preparatory work for a long paper that highlights innovation processes.

2 Theoretical Background and Frame

To answer the *first research question*, the nine elements of the Business Model Canvas (BMC), such as key partners, key activities and key resources (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2013) are used. Unplanned adjustments to business models are usually based on changes in the environment. The approach of mapping the business model environment according to Osterwalder and Pigneur (2011) serves to identify and evaluate those changes, using four categories of key forces: Industry forces, market forces, and macroeconomic forces, whereby these are in turn characterized on the basis of 18 external factors.

To answer the *second research question*, the so-called St. Gallen approach is used. Gassmann et al. (2021) emphasize the possibility of focused discussions using their reduced model compared to canvas models. The customer is the focus of the St. Gallen Business Model and forms the first dimension "customer/segment". To describe the target customers, the BMC

categories of the customer segment and customer relationships are listed in the context of this paper, as the communication options are crucial to how the customer segment can be reached. The second dimension "value proposition" describes the offered service/product, which is of benefit to the customer (Gassmann et al., 2021). The two BMC categories of value proposition and channels are thus subsumed under this dimension, as the channels are decisive in how the service/product offered is made available to the customer. The "value chain" forms the third dimension of the St. Gallen Business Model, so that the BMC categories of key partners, key activities and key resources are assigned to this dimension, as these represent the value chain for service provision. The last dimension "profit mechanism" directly targets the cost structure and the revenue mechanisms according to Gassmann et al. (2021), which is why the BMC categories of revenue sources and cost structure are located under this dimension (see Table 1).

Table 5

Theory-Based Categories of Data Collection and Analysis (own compilation)

Business Model Canvas by Osterwalder & Pigneur (2013)								
key partners	key activities	key resources	value propositions	channels	customer relationships	customer segments	cost structure	revenue streams
Value chain			Value propositions		Customer segment		Profit mechanism	
St. Gallen Business Model by Gassmann et al. (2021)								

Business Model Environment by Osterwalder & Pigneur (2011)			
Key trends:	Market forces:	Macro-economic forces:	Industry forces:
- Technology trends	- Market segments	- Global market conditions	- Value chain actors
- Regulatory trends	- Needs and demands	- Capital markets	- Stakeholders
- Socio-cultural trends	- Market Issues	- Resources	- Competitors
- Socioeconomic trends	- Switching costs	- Economic infrastructure	- New entrants
	- Revenue attractiveness		- Substitute products

The following chapter explains the method of data collection with regard to the categories already mentioned in the context of the two funding lines BEX and IBB.

3 Methodology

The sample of the research consists of 18 projects, nine in BEX and nine in IBB. Selected were those cases in which at least one organisation was involved in both funding contexts so that the research design corresponds to a longitudinal study. The analysis is based primarily on project documents, such as application forms, interim and final reports, and documents collected following particular research questions (Business Modell Canvases, interview transcriptions, protocols). This research bases on a document analysis focusing on an organisation-based approach, which is promising despite its limitation: "A high degree of selection and controlled self-presentation" (Schmidt, 2017, p. 447). The advantage lies in a non-reactive approach avoiding the distortion of results, for example through social desirability. In addition, no disruption of organisational processes is necessary. Furthermore, it opens up the possibility of analysing events and assessments that lie in the past (Schmidt, 2017). In a first step, the analysis was conducted to identify adoptions made from the intended/planned to the final business model within each project in each funding program, as well as the related reasoning, where available. In a second step, the kind of adjustments made in BEX and IBB were compared between the funding lines in order to identify differences in this respect.

The data were collected from 2019 until 2022 (continuing in the case of IBB). Interviews lasted between 30 and 90 minutes and were recorded and logged. Table 2 gives an overview of the data included. Two researchers conducted the coding procedure to establish the greatest possible comprehensibility and objectivity. For the transparency of the analysis, an MS Excel document based on the category system was filled with quotations and paraphrases that allowed a conclusion to be drawn about the respective underlying document. The documents were anonymised following a structure to prevent inferences about individual projects.

Table 2
Overview of Data Base (own compilation)

Sources	BEX	IBB
Application form	9	9
Interim report	18	104 ¹
Final report	9	7
Business Modell Canvas	- ²	9
Final interview protocol	9	- ³

Within the first step, the BEX-related documents are analysed following the presented category system (see Table 1). Afterwards, the same was made for the related IBB projects.

4 Analysis

The first research question was: *What adaptations have been made in the course of the projects with regard to the originally planned business models and why?* In a first step, the adaptations made in BEX are shortly presented (4.1) so that subsequently the adjustments within IBB are shown (4.2). The identified changes are structured by the introduced category system. This is followed by a mapping of the adaptations within the business models of the selected IBB projects, applying the Business Model Environment according to Osterwalder and Pigneur (2011). Finally, the adaptation strategies of the projects are located with reference to the reasons (4.3). The detailed findings for the adaptations made in BEX and IBB regarding the business models are presented in the appendix of this paper in Table 4.

The core of a business model is the service provided. To illustrate the project data, Table 3 gives an overview of the identified value propositions as the core of the business models for VET providers in both funding lines.

Table 3
VET Services in BEX and IBB (own compilation)

VET Service	BEX	IBB
Training centres	B1; B4; B7; B8	I1; I4; I7; I8
Education cooperation	B3; B7	I1; I5; I7
Initial training structures and further training offers	B3; B4; B5; B6; B7	I4; I5; I6; I7; I9
Further training system	B9	-
Contribution to system	-	I3; I5; I9
Development & distribution of VET services	B1; B2; B6; B7; B9	I2; I3; I6

¹ The high number of analyzed interim reports in IBB results from the design of the funding line, as each project partner had to submit a separate interim report annually during the project period.

² This data was not available for the BEX funding program as the scientific monitoring of that context applied other methods for their research.

³ Will be respected in a journal contribution.

In the case of BEX, these were (1) the establishment of training centres or specialised academies (B1; B4; B7; B8), (2) initialisation of education cooperation (B3; B7), (3) establishment of initial training structures and further training offers (B3; B4; B5; B7), (4) development of a further training system (B9), (5) development of digital VET offers (B6) and (6) distribution of vocational training services (including digital services and licensing; B1; B2; B7; B9).

For IBB, there were the (1) establishment of training centres or specialised academies or competence centres (including the support of local partners with the establishment: I1; I4; I7; I8), (2) initialisation of education cooperation (I1; I5; I7), (3) establishment of initial training structures and further training offers (I4; I5; I6; I7; I9), (4) contribution to existing VET systems in the project country (I3; I5; I9), (5) development and distribution of vocational training services (including the support of local partners: I2; I3; I6). Two aspects can be observed: Firstly, the aspect of development, testing and implementation of VET services appears in a union. Secondly, nearly half of the projects were constantly referred to the choice of the value proposition; however, the picture is highly diverse. Overall, it is noticeable that the dual aspect was named much more clearly in IBB than in BEX.

4.1 Adaptions in the BEX Funding Line

The aim of this funding line was the development of a sustainable business model in the context of VET at the international level. That means for possible adaptions a strong relation to the development of such business models and a probably wide range of those through all dimensions of the development processes.

At first, it can be stated that the projects in BEX all followed a systematic business model development approach related to common models (Bullinger & Scheer, 2006; Leimeister, 2020). Development phases, such as start phase, analysis, conception, preparation, testing and implementation (Bullinger & Scheer, 2006) are recognizable. This allows to compare the developed business models since they all refer to the same theoretical frame. Subsequently, the dimensions of the BMC are described based on the projects' data.

In a first step, the adjustments identified for the adaption processes in BEX are described. Most changes relate to the BMC elements *value proposition*, *customer relationships*, *cost structure* and *channels*. Changes within the first mentioned categories were the increasing importance of customer-related adaptions (use of new terms, such as "cooperation" (B3), "overcoming distance [...], transparency and trust" (B6) instead of vague ideas). Here, there was a reevaluation of a rather technical understanding of customer relations identified. Moreover, a stronger combination of novelty (VET service in a new market) with customer involvement took place (see i.e. case B3 in Table 4). Finally, the creation of new business segments was observed ("change of the country necessary", B2; "consultancy for German customers", B1; B7).

Adaptions regarding customer relationships showed that descriptions of those relations developed from a rather vague resp. a technical and unsorted collection to a precise and differentiated state within the BEX program, including a new value base for the relations, created.

The changes relevant to cost structure addressed the reduction of fixed costs, where possible, while variable costs were chosen as a basis for a business model (i.e. B3; B6). Channels, finally, showed a growing combination of direct channels and stronger customer involvement according to the adaption process (B3; B6).

Overall, in BEX the involvement of customers stands out in terms of business model adaptions. However, there were some aspects confirmed by the actors, in detail a low-threshold contact offer for customers (*key activities*), the weight of the key resources on intellectual and human resources (*key resources*), the addressed customer segments (*customer segments*) and participation fees as the main *revenue stream*. Transferred to the introduced model of Business Model Environment, these changes can be mainly described as driven by market forces (Market

Segments - Needs & Demands; Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011). In some cases, crises arose that had to be managed by the actors. These are political changes resp. crises (key trends/regulatory trends), (unexpected) competitors at the target market (industry forces/competitors) and loss of project partners (industry forces/stakeholders).

4.2 Adaptions in the IBB Funding Line

The aim of the IBB funding line was also the development of a sustainable business model regarding a selected target country, whereby the focus here is to a greater extent on the establishment of cooperation. Just like the analysed projects from the BEX funding line, the IBB projects followed a systematic business model development approach, whereby the approach of Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013) was applied directly to enable comparability of the cases. The following is a brief description of the main factors causing changes in the business models of the IBB projects (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2011). Changes do not occur evenly across the nine IBB projects in all nine areas of the Business Model Canvas. Changes are particularly evident in the categories of key partners, key activities, key resources, value propositions, and channels. Much less affected are the categories of customer relationships, customer segments, cost structure, and revenue sources (see Table 4 in the appendix).

Adaptions in the category of key partners are mainly made towards changes at the personnel level on the part of the involved partners in the target country (Industry Forces - Stakeholders), so that in some projects new partners have been added (see the cases I2, I3, I4, I7 in Table 4), while in others some have been cancelled (see the cases I3, I5, I6 in Table 4). Changes in key activities in the projects include permanent and continuous adaptation to the situation and needs in the target country (Market Forces - Needs & Demands; see the cases I3, I4, I5, and I6 in Table 4). In addition, new challenges arise based on the pandemic, resulting in a changed market with new competitors (Industry Forces – Competitors; see the cases I1, I2, and I8 in Table 4). Adjustments to key resources arise in the analysed projects primarily as a result of the pandemic so that changes are only indirectly attributable to factors in the BMC environment. Changes to the value proposition result primarily from changes in the needs of partners in the target country with regard to the scope and content of the VET service, so that the focus in most projects shifts to further training measures and modularization of the offering (Industry Forces - Stakeholders & Market Forces - Needs and Demands; see Table 3 and the adaptions of the cases I1, I3, I8 in Table 4).

Adjustments in customer relationships increasingly exist with regard to digital communication, whereby the importance of personal and direct communication is also emphasized (Industry Forces – Stakeholders; see cases I1, I2, I3, I4 in Table 4). Channels to increase awareness of the VET service could not be perceived in part due to the pandemic, so there was an increased shift to digital channels (political crisis; not to be located in the BMC environment). Significant changes in customer segments were not made. Changes in the cost structure and revenue streams arise with regard to the reallocation of financial resources (see the cases I1, I2, I3, I5, and I6 in Table 4) on the part of the project associations due to the lack of financial support of the local partners and the resulting lack of sales opportunities (Macro-Economic Forces - Capital Markets; Market Forces - Market Issues & Revenue Attractiveness).

To summarize the results with regard to the first research question: What adjustments were made with respect to the originally planned business model development and why? It should be noted that adjustments to the business models are primarily determined by the factors "Industry Forces - Stakeholders" and "Market Forces - Needs and Demands" (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011). In addition, a considerable extent of the adjustments to the business models can be attributed to pandemic-related factors.

4.3 Strategic orientation of the Developed Business Models

The second research question was: (2) *What can we learn about the strategic orientation of the adaptations identified?* In order to answer this question, the analysed projects from the BEX and IBB funding lines were classified in terms of their degree of adjustments in relation to the categories of the business model. Subsequently, the strategy of adaption of the projects can be derived from this. In order to work out the core elements of the adaptations of the business models, the St. Gallen Business Model by Gassmann and Frankenberger (2016)⁴ was used. This approach provides the four dimensions of customer/segment, value propositions, value chain and revenue mechanism. The BMC business model with its nine categories can thus be directly transferred to the St. Gallen Business Model⁵. This approach of Gassmann et al. (2013, 2021) serves to reduce the complexity of the data in a way that allows a comparison of business models regarding their main strategic orientation when adjusting their business model to relevant needs. The results of the reduction are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Strategic Orientation of the Adaptions of the Developed Business Models (own compilation)

Project	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9
Customer/segment	x	x	x				x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Value proposition	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Value chain				x	x			x	x	x	x	x	x			x		x
Profit mechanism																		

Overall, it can be seen that various reasons for adaptations of the business models can be identified across the two funding lines regarding the four dimensions in Table 5. Adjustments based on the loss of a project partner occur in two projects in different dimensions of the business model (B1: Customer/segment, I5: Value chain). Adjustments to the business model as a result of political changes are also found in two projects in different dimensions (B2: Customer/segment, I5: Value proposition). Moreover, three projects report adjustments to their business model as a reaction to unforeseen competitors (B2: Customer/segments, I1: Value propositions, I9: Value chain).

Adjustments due to the unexpected digitalization of customer relationships caused by the pandemic are found in all IBB projects in the dimension of the customer/segments, as well as the unexpected expansion of digital channels in the dimension of value propositions as a reason for pandemic-related changes. To avoid the cancellation of the project as a consequence of the loss of the project partner, two projects have made adaptations in the dimension of the value chain (B4, B5). Furthermore, adaptations of the service based on the needs of the partners in the project country are found in two of the nine IBB projects (I1: Value chain, I3: Value proposition). One IBB project also had to adjust the value chain because of the difficulty of finding partners in the target country (I3).

For BEX, two main patterns of adjustments can be observed. Either the business models are adapted with a scope on customers and value proposition, or the changes are made with a scope on value proposition and value chain. In the dimension "customer/segment", changes can be attributed i.a. to the loss of project partners (B1), political changes and unforeseen competitors (industry forces/competitors; B2). The case of profit mechanisms is difficult, as there is a recognizable shift away from fixed costs without concrete numbers to evaluate concrete adaptations. When comparing both groups within BEX, it shows that one more project in the value-

⁴ First published in Gassmann et al. (2013).

⁵ The assignment of the BMC categories to the four dimensions of the St. Gallen Model can be found in Table 1.

focused pattern was cancelled. One project focused on value proposition and did not provide clear data for the assignment of other innovation indicators.

For the IBB projects, the picture is in some respects different from the adjustment patterns of the BEX projects. Basically, it should be noted that based on the Covid pandemic, the IBB projects had to make adaptations in the category of customer relationships (customer/segment) and in the category of channels (value chain) in order to maintain project activities during the pandemic. This aspect can be treated as a limitation of the research since it is not possible to make assumptions about what changes would probably not have been made without that special situation. In the IBB projects, however, it seems that the adjustment strategies focus on the dimensions of value propositions and value chain, which can be attributed i.e. to the adaptation of the value proposition to the needs of partners in the project country and to the expansion of key partners due i.e. to the loss of other partners (new focus). An alternative interpretation would be that adaptations concerning the customer/segment dimension would have been made without the context of the pandemic and that this factor only worked as a driver. This aspect needs further investigation; at the same time, the analysed data suggest an increase in customer orientation from BEX to IBB (see Table 4 in the appendix).

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The results show similarities as well as differences regarding changes compared to the originally planned business models and the actual design of these at the end of the funding period of the projects in both funding programs. While in BEX the business models of the analysed projects are adjusted either in terms of customers and value proposition or in terms of value proposition and value chain, the business models of the IBB projects are adjusted mainly in terms of the dimensions of value propositions and value chain. At the same time, it should be noted that certain adjustments in the direction of the digitalization of channels and relationships with customers seemed inevitable due to the pandemic. In summary, factors relating to stakeholders and competitors (industry forces), as well as needs and demands in the target country (market forces), are the main reasons for changes in business models during the project (see Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011). Increasing alignment with local structures, key partners, networks and also political support in the target country (see appendix Table 4) can be seen as a strategy of German VET SMEs abroad, which lack the necessary resources for larger ventures outside such funding contexts. A growing efficiency in resource planning and the increasing involvement of local partners indicate that SMEs have learned to compensate for their weaknesses in international markets, which can be assumed by comparing the BEX and IBB programs. These new strategic orientations of the projects can probably be considered innovations in this context.

It can be assumed that major adaptations cannot be afforded by the majority of the analysed players. The digitalization of certain factors of the business models can possibly be understood as an innovation driver so that larger developments and innovations could be expected in the area of product innovation. However, the pandemic-driven digitalisation caused a certain number of adaptations made in the field of customers/segments. The strong orientation towards customers can also mean that innovations must be closely monitored, even or especially if they are imposed. This would explain the strong process orientation within most of the projects that serve to align the adaptation to the needs of the customers. This statement would confirm "the emerging interest of innovation research in small improvements" (Schulz-Schaeffer, 2021, p. 35; translated by the authors) so that innovations are often incremental and closely controlled (Schulz-Schaeffer, 2021). Other explanations cannot be excluded, though, such as the possibility that radical innovation is hindered by the funding rules and procedures applying to IBB and BEX. This aspect needs to be addressed in the course of further research.

The providers also have a high level of problem-solving expertise due to the consortium approach, as well as to their international experience. The growth of know-how in digital teaching and digital communication channels can lead to changed business models for VET service providers in the long term, and further research in this area would be worth pursuing.

In the context of this paper, the question thus arises as to the innovation content of the projects analysed in the two funding programs: What degree of innovation could be recorded in the context of the projects considered and the data basis presented? Are there any patterns of innovation emerging from VET providers' internationalisation processes and how do both aspects relate?

This research is mainly limited by the context of the funding program. Moreover, the sample consists of German VET providers. Nevertheless, in times of globalisation, SMEs from all over the world can take part in internationalisation processes. The findings of this study may serve as an example of what VET service providers need to take into consideration, in particular when starting businesses abroad. The close relation of resources, and the unique selling point in close exchange with the customers appear relevant aspects also in international contexts.

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Appendix

Table 4

Results of the BMC-Based Analysis of the BEX and IBB Projects (own compilation)

Dimension of BMC	BEX starting idea (application form)	BEX final form (interim and final report)	IBB starting idea (application form and Business Modell Canvas)	IBB final form (interim and final report)
Key partners	German Economic partners in project country (B1; B2; B4; B8) Organisations of project country in Germany (B3; B6) Partner organisations in project country (B3; B5; B7) active design of relation to competitors (B2)	expanded or supplemented on a project-specific basis: involvement of universities in project country (B8) involvement of German chamber of commerce in project country (B9)	Companies in project country (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9), German Economic partners in project country (I2, I6, I9), educational institutions in project country (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9), associations & chambers (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I7, I9), authorities & ministries (I1, I2, I3, I4, I6, I9). Translators (I9)	Expanded cooperation in project country: Cooperation with state governments (I2), Institute for Vocational Education (I3) & Associations/chambers (I7) & companies (I4, I7). Cancelled as partner in project country: Universities (I6), Ministry of Education (I3) & educational cooperation partner in the project country (I5).
Key activities	Demonstration of dual elements (B1) Further education and train-the-trainer activities (B1; B2; B3; B6) Digital offers (B2; B9) Establishment of an educational institution (B4; B5; B7; B8) active promotion using well-known label (B1)	Low-threshold contact offer has been confirmed, customer focus has become even stronger online promotion extended network creation more important (B4; B8)	Networking (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9) Research & development (I5, I6, I9) Establishing sales opportunities (I6, I7) Measures to increase the attractiveness of vocational education (I3) Establishment of an educational institution (I1, I8) Digital learning offer (I1, I2, I6, I9)	Due to the pandemic, all projects had to digitally reorganize or postpone their activities, which included e.g. the evaluation of the project (I3), work process analyses (I7), the communication with partners and implementation of the educational services in the project country (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9).
Key resources	physical resources (B1; B2; B5) intellectual resources (B1; B2; B3; B4; B5; B6; B9) financial resources (B2) human resources (B1; B2; B3; B4; B5; B6; B7; B8; B9)	the distribution with weight on intellectual and human resources did not change; in opposite, it was confirmed by increasing use of popular labels (B1; B8) and cooperation became more important	Human resources (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I9) Physical resources (I1, I2, I3, I7) Intellectual resources (I1, I2, I4, I5, I6, I8, I9) Business premises in project country (I9) Proven educational services (I4, I5) Financial resources (I7)	Changes occur, among others, with regard to the loss of personnel resources (I1, I3) & the lack of possibility to obtain course materials through sanctions (I5). The potential of digital media, including learning videos (I7) and know-how on digital teaching (I3), has been added as a resource.
Value proposition	Training programmes modelled on the German dual model (B1; B2; B3; B4; B6; B7; B8), Novelty of VET service in specific markets (first mover: B2; B5; B8; B9; early follower: B3; B1; B4; B6) Support of suppliers in project country (B2; B8), certification of achieved competences (B3; B5; B9), combination of novelty with concomitant customer-related offers (B3)	customer related adaptations (B7; B8) combination of novelty with concomitant customer-related offers intensified (B3; B6; B7) enabling customers to problem-solving creation of new business segments (B2; B7)	Establishment of a certification system (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5), development of consulting services (I1, I3, I6, I7, I9), offering further VET (I2, I3, I5, I6, I9), offering initial VET (I4, I7), offering initial & further VET (I1, I8), train-the-trainer-activities (I1, I2, I8, I9), career orientation activities (I3), selling the trademark "Made in Germany" (I4, I5, I6, I7, I9)	Reduction of the compexity of the VET service (I1, I3, I8) Customer related adaptations (I3, I4, I5, I6) Change in the initial situation due to competitors (I1, I2, I8) Adding additional value propositions (I3, I4, I8) Pandemic-related omission of full testing of VET service, only piloting (I3)

Customer relationships	Events with public effectiveness (B1; B2; B3; B5; B6; B8), public Relations and Marketing (B1; B3; B4; B5; B6; B8) active design of customer-supplier-relation (B1; B2; B5; B7), information material and platforms (B1; B2; B5; B7; B8; B9), Creation of business cooperation (B2), Addressing leaders and managers (B2; B4), co-creative relations (B2; B9), addressing the German community (B5; B7)	rather vague formulations about the customer relation become clear and differentiated during the project duration. Marketing goals and relationship building are thought of more strongly together New terms are: Cooperation, overcoming distance, facilitating entry, transparency and trust, which show a reevaluation of the customer relations	Long-term cooperation and regular contacts (I1, I2, I7, I9) Accessibility after implementation (I2) Direct and personal contact (I1, I5, I6, I9) Friendly business relations (I1, I3) Exchange and innovation impulses for both sides (I3, I4) Platform-based relationships (I6)	Customer relationships continue to be characterized by direct contact, at the same time a strong increase in digital communication channels can be seen (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9). Due to the pandemic, most of the communication between the involved partners took place exclusively digitally.
Channels	use of direct channels (B1; B2; B4; B7; B8; B9) involvement of partners with customer data bases (B3; B5)	connection of both as lesson learned from development process (B6)	Social media (I1, I2, I3, I5, I9) Websites/homepages (I1, I2, I5, I7, I9) personal contact (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5) conferences & transfer events (I2, I6, I7) Publications/Flyers/brochures (I1, I2, I5)	Due to the pandemic, channels are also becoming increasingly digital due to lack of presence in the target country (I1, I2, I3, I4), trade show visits have been eliminated (I1, I3), involvement of project partners in project country for marketing increased (I1)
Customer segments	VET teachers (B1; B2; B3; B5; B7; B8) Skilled workers/management in companies (B2; B3; B5; B7; B9) Training staff and/or apprentices/students (B1; B7; B8) further education staff/multipliers (B1; B2), German VET service providers (B6; B9), Particular target groups without VET background (B4)	customer segments were not changed during development process with regard to the follow-up funding line, the largest segments were confirmed, while the further education segment increased	vocational schools & students (I1, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8), Pupils (vocational orientation) (I3), Colleges/universities (I1, I4, I5, I7), Teachers (I1, I7, I8), Businesses & employees (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9), Suppliers (I2), Associations (I2, I3, I9), Public and private educational institutions (I1, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9), regional administration (I4)	The customer segments have not changed significantly, only a smaller number of the target group could be reached (I5) or universities have not been further addressed as customers (I7).
Cost structure	Rent, material and administration when setting up the infrastructure on site (B1) variable costs cannot be defined clearly at project start Sales savings (B6)	general development reduction of fix costs and choice of variable costs as basis for cost structure	Personnel costs (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9), training materials (I3, I5, I6) IT infrastructure and technical equipment (I1, I2, I3, I6, I7, I9), marketing & advertising (I1, I3, I5, I9), translator and interpreter costs (I1, I3, I6, I9), facilities in project country (I1, I4, I6, I9), course/module development (I2, I3, I6, I9), Travel costs (I2, I5, I6, I9), partner costs (I5), Certification (I9)	Shift in cost structure in favor of personnel costs (I1, I4, I5, I8), reduction in travel costs due to the pandemic (I1, I2, I3, I5, I6). Funding from an educational partner in the target country no longer possible due to changed economic situation (I5).
Revenue streams	Licences (B3; B4; B6; B9) Participation fees (B1; B2; B4; B5; B7; B8) Consulting (B3; B6; B8) (Development and) sale of material and equipment (B1; B3; B7)	Participation fees remain the vast part of revenue streams Licensing decreases, while sale of modules and programmes in VET and CVET increases	Certification/license fees (I2, I5, I6, I8), public tenders of government in target country (I4), consulting fees (I5, I6, I7), software as a service (I6), trainings/workshops & participant fees (I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9)	Focus remains on revenue from participant fees. Funding by the governments of the project country is no longer the focus & licensing as a source was discarded after examination (I2). Cost-neutral extension of the project (I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7).